

Deliverable 1.4.2

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Work Package leader	EMBL-EBI
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Abstract: This deliverable is a comprehensive report of the PhenoMeNal consortium's activities and performance towards meeting the objectives and goals of the project from M7 - M12 (inclusive).	

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this second period of report from M7-M12 (March - August 2016), PhenoMeNal has continued its work towards establishing a comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for data processing, analysing and information mining of extremely large medical metabolic phenotype data. During these six months, the consortium work was focussed on interfacing and reporting on requirements of biomedical infrastructures, identifying community accepted data standards, development of a Virtual Research Environment (VRE) portal, Virtual machine images (VMIs) and develop a sustainability model for the PhenoMeNal project. With the goal of including experts in the relevant domains, particularly in cloud computing and storage and analysis of big data, the consortium joined forces with CRS4 (Center For Advanced Studies, Research And Development In Sardinia) a member of the Italian national node of BBMRI-ERIC (BBMRI.it). A grant agreement was submitted in this context. Privacy and ethics activities was integrated across all work packages to ensure ethical, legal and social compliance across the entire project.

1.1. Description of work performed and main results

As part of the effective management of the consortium activities, monthly project coordination meetings, individual and cross-work package hangouts and project weekly updates in form of email communications were carried out. The overall progress of the project was monitored using Pivotal tracker, an online tool for project management. The consortium activities were reviewed independently during the first interim review held at Brussels in March 2016, and independent stakeholder and scientific advisory board (SAB) meetings held in June 2016 respectively.

A comprehensive sustainability plan which details business models options as well as the design choices and risk mitigation if any of the components fails to be sustainable, was designed. An industry workshop was hosted in order to raise awareness of the PhenoMeNal initiative and to ensure optimal interoperability of PhenoMeNal infrastructure and instrument vendor's data formats and tools. Resulting from these activities, an industry panel was established which would be consulted for specifications and challenges from an industry point of view. A questionnaire to gather requirements on the use of metabolomics by large research centers and infrastructures was circulated to maximise communications with other infrastructures with similar initiatives. These institutions were also involved in a discussion on future applications of metabolomics,

and setting up of a working group on metabolomics in systems biology involving partners of the ISBE ¹(Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe).

The development of the PhenoMeNal VRC (Virtual Research Community, static) Portal was initiated by requirement analysis through a User Experience (UX) workshop. A user feedback component was included to facilitate constructive feedback, bug reporting and feature request, that will help drive the development of the PhenoMeNal general website, VRE and the tools therein.

As part of defining data standards, a survey was launched to narrow down on standards requirements in metabo- and phenomics, the ISA and the nmrML data standards were overhauled and work on an evidence code ontology for metabolite identifications.

The containerisation of preprocessing tools is the first crucial step that all the workflows depend on, as the conversion into open source community standards and formats allows to further process the data in a vendor-agnostic manner. In this context, a successful initial containerisation (Virtual Machine Images) of RAW file converters for MS and NMR data was achieved.

As for dissemination and outreach, the project website was further developed and updated. Dissemination material in form of presentations, posters, and blog posts on the website were produced. Several workshops, staff-exchanges and training programs were conducted for knowledge management within the consortium as well as with the user community.

2. OBJECTIVES, WORK PROGRESS, ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROJECT MANAGEMENT

2.1. Project objectives for the period

During this period, the consortium has continued to work towards the following general project objectives:

- To integrate existing open source tools and methods for the management, dissemination and computational analysis of very large datasets of human

¹ <http://project.isbe.eu>

metabolic phenotyping and genomic data into a secure and sustainable e-infrastructure.

- To operate and consolidate the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure based on existing internal and external HPC and grid resources, including the EGI, and to extend it to worldwide grid infrastructures.
- To improve and scale up tools within the infrastructure to cope with very large datasets.
- To establish technology for a water-tight audit trail for the processing of human metabolic phenotyping data from the raw data acquisition all the way to the generation of high-level biomedical insights.
- To establish privacy-protection methods that allow working with highly sensitive molecular phenotype data.
- To foster the worldwide adoption of PhenoMeNal through a wide range of outreach, dissemination, networking and training activities.
- To develop a model to ensure sustainability of PhenoMeNal.

These project objectives were pursued through the combination of the project's networking activities (WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4), service activities (WP5 and WP6) and joint research activities (WP7, WP8 and WP9):

- Identification of requirements of research and industry centres that produce or make use of metabolomics and other 'omics data.
- Identification of data exchange and storage standards while improving and scaling up tools.
- Deployment of a Continuous Integration (CI) (Jenkins)² instance as a focal point of PhenoMeNal development to gather the building of all tools, package them into virtual machines or software containers, carry out unit testing, and publish the components to public repositories and dedicated PhenoMeNal repositories.
- Creation of a PhenoMeNal VRC Portal (currently partly static) as the entry point (gateway) to all the tools and workflows.
- Developing a model for PhenoMeNal sustainability.
- Production of guidance document on appropriate policies, procedures and management of sensitive human data.
- Identification of test datasets as use cases with listing of ethical permissions.
- Workshops and training activities to disseminate and promote the service provided by PhenoMeNal across a wide-range of scientific and industrial sectors.

The main deliverables achieved during this period were:

² <https://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>

No.	Deliverable name	WP No	Lead participant	Delivery date	Status
D1.4.2	Bi-annual progress report	1	EMBL-EBI	M12	Submitted
D1.3	Minutes of kick-off meeting (revised)	1	EMBL-EBI	M2	Re-submitted
D1.4.1	Bi-annual progress report (revised)	1	EMBL-EBI	M6	Re-submitted
D1.5.1	Data management plan (revised)	1	EMBL-EBI	M6	Re-submitted
D2.2	Sustainability plan from all participating sites regarding their components of the PhenoMeNal grid infrastructure	2	UL	M12	Submitted
D2.1	Report on mapping of e-infrastructures, users, investments for supporting policy developments in field of metabolomics, biomarkers and biobanks	2	UL	M6	Re-submitted
D3.1.1	Report of the annual stakeholder meeting	3	UoB	M12	Submitted
D4.1	Report on requirements for relevant research centers producing and/or consuming metabolomics data with respect to computational aspects, data storage, and infrastructural needs	4	CIRMMP	M12	Submitted

D5.1	Build System with continuous integration, providing development snapshots of PhenoMeNal Virtual Machine Images	5	UU	M9	Submitted
D5.2	A beta-version of PhenoMeNal integration VMI capable of proof-of-concept integration with other VMIs. Initial services online supporting PhenoMeNal data standards	5	UU	M12	Submitted
D6.2	PhenoMeNal VRC (static) portal publicly available	6	EMBL-EBI	M12	Submitted
D6.3	Online user feedback form	6	EMBL-EBI	M12	Submitted
D7.3	Evaluation report for the introduction of a data provider form	7	ICL	M8	Submitted
D7.4	Process to extract maximum information from sensitive datasets with minimum compromise, in collaboration with BBMRI and BioMedBridges	7	ICL	M12	Submitted
D7.5	Report to the EC/REA with ethical approvals, informed consent forms and patient information material of datasets to be	7	ICL	M8	Submitted

	used within PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure development				
D8.1	Report on community standards for reporting, access and integrity supported in the PhenoMeNal grid; to be disseminated in a dedicated BioSharing page and via the project website	8	UOXF	M12	Submitted
D9.2.1	<i>PhenoMeNal-Preprocess</i> Virtual Machine Image to enable data producers to locally process raw data into standard formats supported in PhenoMeNal	9	IPB	M12	Submitted

Table 1. List of deliverables submitted until M12

Milestones achieved during this period:

No	Milestone name	WP No	Lead participant	Delivery date	Status
MS2.1	Sustainability Plan released	2	UL	M12	Achieved
MS4.1	Establishment of first working group	4	CIRMMP	M12	Achieved
MS6.2	Initial release of PhenoMeNal VRC portal online	6	EMBL-EBI	M12	Achieved
MS8.1	Initial analysis of	8	UOXF	M12	Achieved

	community standards finalised				
MS9.1	Integration of <i>initially</i> supported tools into Jenkins system for continuous integration		IPB	M12	Achieved

Table 2. List of Milestones achieved until M12

2.2. Work Progress and Achievements during this period

WP2 – Sustainability of PhenoMeNaI

WP Leader: University of Leiden (UL)

During the reporting period, the main achievements were:

- An initial version of the sustainability plan for PhenoMeNaI was achieved.
- Active engagement with the industrial and academic users for wider acceptance of PhenoMeNaI in the community. An industry panel has been established in this respect.
- Design of business models for sustainability including mitigation of risks identified.

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period:

Task 2.2 Create a first version of the sustainability plan, which details business models options as well as the design choices and risk mitigation if any of the components fails to be sustainable.

Following the recommendations from the SAB, industry panel and exhaustive discussions during the annual consortium meeting, an initial strategy for the PhenoMeNaI sustainability and acceptance within a wider user community was conceived (see deliverable **D2.2**). This plan would include:

- a) The overall technical sustainability of PhenoMeNal, the design choices and risk mitigation if any of the components fails to be sustainable.
- b) Engagement with both industrial and academic users in order to get PhenoMeNal widely accepted in the community.
- c) Different business models options for the long term sustainability of the PhenoMeNal research infrastructure.

As part of defining a business model for the PhenoMeNal infrastructure, an e-infrastructure ecosystem comprising of research infrastructures in biomedicine and systems biology, as well as other e-infrastructures, which together provide cloud computing, data services, biological samples and medical technologies and their interaction with PhenoMeNal was conceived (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 PhenoMeNal ecosystem

In terms of technical sustainability, in order to establish a comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure for analysing medical metabolic data, improvement of existing data analysis software tools, and development of new ones only if they are missing links required in the workflows, was considered one of the upstream first-principles. Additionally, establishment and adaptation of the middleware, and integration of the aforementioned data analysis methods was also perceived as important. In all cases, the main aim is to contribute to the upstream software project, such that the developments become part of the normal code development, testing and maintenance.. This way the software basis of the PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure will be available beyond the runtime of project.

Potential risks associated with the software components associated with the PhenoMeNal infrastructure and their mitigation strategies were also identified as part of risk management under the technical sustainability of PhenoMeNal.

Several engagement-dependent business models identifying measures to broaden the range of potential users and raising awareness of PhenoMeNal services and tools were also determined as part of the sustainability plan for PhenoMeNal.

Future plans:

- Working towards a business plan that would satisfy the overall goal of PhenoMeNal.
- Establishing contacts with publishers for supporting data deposition services.

WP3 – Dissemination and Outreach

WP leader: University of Birmingham (UoB)

In this period, the consortium has worked further towards establishing working relationships with the potential user community and relevant infrastructures at the European level, including ISBE³, Eu-OpenScreen⁴, BBMRI⁵ (Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure), ELIXIR⁶, and national level, such as the Netherlands Metabolomics Centre⁷ (NL) and MetaboHub⁸ (FR). The CORBEL (Coordinated Research Infrastructures Building Enduring Life-science Services) project⁹ has been approached as well, as it is a network of eleven European biological and medical research infrastructures (BMS RIs). All project partners have been actively involved in presenting PhenoMeNal's aims and activities at various events and dissemination channels. Training events and workshops were organised to ensure wider outreach and uptake in the user community.

The main achievements during the reporting period are:

³ <http://project.isbe.eu>

⁴ <http://www.eu-openscreen.eu>

⁵ <http://bbmri-eric.eu>

⁶ <https://www.elixir-europe.org>

⁷ <http://www.metabolomicscentre.nl>

⁸ <http://www.metabohub.fr/index.php?lang=en>

⁹ <http://www.corbel-project.eu/home.html>

- Redevelopment of the project website with a new Wiki page¹⁰.
- Organisation of workshop on Metabolic Phenotyping in Clinical practice.
- Organisation of a workshop/hackathon on the Galaxy environment for workflow management.
- Annual stakeholder meeting (see deliverable **D3.1.1**).
- Industry workshop engaging instrument vendors to raise awareness of the PhenoMeNal initiative and to ensure optimal interoperability of PhenoMeNal infrastructure and instrument vendor's data formats and tools.
- Presentation of PhenoMeNal at various national and international events (see list as appended below).

A summary of the progress of the work in the reporting period;

Task 3.1 We will initially employ the usual channels for the dissemination of PhenoMeNal tools and services, including scientific publications, workshops and presentations at the metabolomics conferences to reach the wider metabolomics community.

The preliminary project website launched after the project kick-off in September 2015 was developed further in parallel to the development of the PhenoMeNal VRC portal and continuously adapted for broader outreach within the consortium as well as to the user community (see Figure 2).

¹⁰ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/wiki/#>

PhenoMeNaL
Large-Scale Computing for Medical Metabolomics

About us Open Ticket Outreach Project Structure Wiki Help

PhenoMeNaL (Phenome and Metabolome aNalysis)
It is a comprehensive and standardised e-infrastructure that will support the data processing and analysis pipelines for molecular phenotype data generated by metabolomics applications. PhenoMeNaL will provide services enabling computation and analysis to improve the understanding of the causes and mechanisms underlying health, healthy ageing and diseases.

Latest News

PhenoMeNaL Consortium Annual Meeting in Rhodes

By David Johnson No Comments Events, Outreach

In June 2016, the PhenoMeNaL project held its first annual consortium meeting, as well as convening meetings for potential stakeholders of the PhenoMeNaL e-infrastructure, and for the project's Scientific Advisory Board. The meetings were held over three days on the historic Dodecanese island of Rhodes, Greece. Stakeholder meeting in Rhodes...

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Tweets by @PhnmiH2020

PhenoMeNaL-H2020 Retweeted

Dr Legido-Quigley @MetabolomicsHub

Date 3rd meeting! 13th Sep @imperialcollege : "New approaches in clinical #metabolomics" #8guestspeakers #LMN16

Figure 2. PhenoMeNaL Website

A PhenoMeNaL H2020 Wiki was integrated into the project website to provide documentation, guidelines and tutorials on PhenoMeNaL technical architecture including usage and development of PhenoMeNaL VRE's. The pages are created, updated and maintained by the PhenoMeNaL developers as markdown files at the GitHub¹¹ hosted wiki which is replicated every two hours at the project site through git pulls and HTML rendering of the markdown code. The wiki holds technical documentation, guides and tutorials for PhenoMeNaL developers and external users, on topics such as deployment of the infrastructure, usage of docker for image preparation, use of the container orchestration layer (Kubernetes) and other similar contents (see Figure 3).

¹¹ <https://github.com/phnmi/phenomenal-h2020/wiki>

PhenoMeNal H2020 wiki

PhenoMeNal provides Virtual Research Environments (VRE) for interoperable and scalable metabolomics analysis. This wiki holds information pertaining to its usage and development.

PhenoMeNal Users

The PhenoMeNal infrastructure will be available for deployment in public and private clouds, as well as local hardware. The main access for users will be through our Virtual Research Environment (VRE).

- [Overview of the PhenoMeNal landscape](#)
- [Using the PhenoMeNal VRE on a public cloud provider](#)
- [Using the PhenoMeNal VRE on a local infrastructure \(e.g. private server, private cloud\)](#)
- [Vocabulary and definitions in PhenoMeNal](#)

PhenoMeNal Developers

PhenoMeNal Developers maintains all the components that enable the VRE, including setting up the virtual infrastructures, continuous integration, developing and containerizing tools, and providing means and resources for extensive testing of all components.

Documents and Guidelines

- [Overview of the PhenoMeNal architecture](#)
- [Deploying PhenoMeNal on OpenStack](#)
- [e-infrastructure requirements for provisioning PhenoMeNal VRE on local systems](#)
- [How to make your software tool available through PhenoMeNal](#)
- [Continuous Integration of software tools in PhenoMeNal](#)
- [Notes on container streamlining, testing & statistics \(Merge-Google-doc-here\)](#)
- [Configure Workflows and Microservices](#)

Tutorials

- [Using Docker](#)

- [Wiki Home](#)
- [Continuous-Integration-in-PhenoMeNal](#)
- [Deploy-your-workflow-with-Ansible](#)
- [Deploying-PhenoMeNal-on-OpenStack](#)
- [Galaxy-inside-Kubernetes](#)
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- [Galaxy-outside-Kubernetes](#)
- [How-to-make-your-software-tool-available-through-PhenoMeNal](#)
- [Starting-up-a-PhenoMeNal-VRE-on-OpenStack](#)
- [Using-Docker](#)
- [Using-docker-compose](#)
- [Using-kubernetes](#)
- [Vocabulary-and-definitions-in-PhenoMeNal](#)
- [Windows-mini-kube](#)
- [eInfra-requirements-local-systems](#)
- [galaxy-with-k8s](#)

Figure 3. PhenoMeNal Wiki

The consortium continued to use its established Twitter channel forming a community around Metabolomics and other e-infrastructure initiatives to disseminate project outputs and events.

TWEET HIGHLIGHTS

Top Tweet earned 1,012 impressions

The journal [@GigaScience](#) has kindly published a guest blog post about our project and data survey [twitter.com/GigaScience/st...](#)

↻ 1 ♥ 3

[View Tweet activity](#)

[View all Tweet activity](#)

Top mention earned 37 engagements

Project Kel

@ProjectKel · Jul 14

PhenoMeNal ([@PhnmIH2020](#)), led by EBI ([@emblem](#)), uses [#pykube](#) ([#Python](#) + [#k8s](#)) for [@galaxyproject](#). On GitHub → [bit.ly/29ASftl](#)

↻ 4 ♥ 4

[View Tweet](#)

Top Follower followed by 5,703 people

Scientific Data

@ScientificData [FOLLOWS YOU](#)

An [#openaccess](#) publication from Nature Research for the descriptions of [#scientifically](#) valuable [#datasets](#).

[View profile](#)

[View followers dashboard](#)

Figure 4. PhenoMeNal twitter analytics (July, 2016)

A workshop on **Metabolic Phenotyping in Clinical practice** was organised by University of Barcelona on 27th May 2016 in collaboration with the Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, IDIBAPS¹² (August Pi i Sunyer Biomedical Research Institute) and the PhenoMeNal consortium to define state-of-the art in metabolic phenotyping in clinics. The workshop was heavily disseminated via blog posts on the project website, twitter and facebook accounts, Metabolomics society¹³, IDIBAPS¹⁴ and CARAMBA¹⁵ (Clinical Analysis & research Applying Mass Spectrometry and Bioinformatics at Akademiska,

¹² http://www.idibaps.org/en_index.html

¹³ <http://metabolomicssociety.org/events/upcoming-conferences-workshops>

¹⁴ http://www.idibaps.org/actualitat/en_agenda/495/several-speakers

¹⁵ <http://www.caramba.clinic/news/metabolic-phenotyping-clinical-practice/>

Uppsala, Sweden) websites. A wordpress website¹⁶ was also created to facilitate registration for interested participants outside the consortium.

Metabolic Phenotyping in Clinical Practice

By Admin

CARAMBA is co-organizing a clinical workshop in Barcelona, Spain

During the workshop multiple aspects of metabolomics such as efficiency, security, and ethical requirements of handling sensitive human data will be discussed with the experts in the fields of biomedicine, ethics, and information technology.

Chris Steinbeck held the opening session about Phenomenal H2020 project. His talk included general description of metabolomics, advantages of the metabolome as a phenotype, complexity, many influences from genes & environment.

In addition, our collaborate Per Johan Jakobsson from Karolinska Institute is presenting exciting results in context of SLE and metabolomics.

Figure 5. Workshop announcement on the CARAMBA Website

The workshop was hosted as a full day event with lightning talks from notable speakers in the field of metabolomics, clinical researchers and data privacy and ethics followed by

¹⁶ www.clinicalworkshopbcn2016.wordpress.com

a discussion to understand the application of metabolomics in clinics, infrastructure needs and role of PhenoMeNal. Some of the presentations from the workshop are available as recordings on the project website¹⁷.

An article as an outcome of this workshop “Clinical Metabolomics: Needs, Success Stories, Problems” is currently under progress.

A workshop/hackathon was organized about the **Galaxy environment**¹⁸, which will be central in PhenoMeNal for the management of the workflows (14th-16th March 2016, CEA, Paris). During the workshop, core members of the Workflow4Metabolomics¹⁹ infrastructure (Christophe Caron, Franck Giacomoni, Gildas Le Corguillé, Etienne Thévenot, Pierrick Roger) presented their experience in building Galaxy tools, testing their functionalities and their installation, and exporting them to the main toolshed, but also on sharing and referencing entire workflows for reproducible research. The EMBL-EBI team presented their work on deploying containers on the cloud via Galaxy, and the possibilities for import/export of MetaboLights²⁰ datasets into Galaxy were discussed. The Galaxy-M project²¹ (presented by Ralf Weber) presented its experience in building and locally running Galaxy modules for Direct Infusion Mass Spectrometry (DIMS). PhenoMeNal partner IPB worked with Luis de la Garza from the OpenMS²² team to propose additional MS processing tools within the PhenoMeNal VRE.

This workshop organized by Workflow4Metabolomics and PhenoMeNal thus gathered developers from and outside the PhenoMeNal consortium to learn, apply, and further develop the cutting-edge Galaxy technology for workflow management.

¹⁷ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/media/>

¹⁸ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/outreach/>

¹⁹ <http://workflow4metabolomics.org>

²⁰ <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>

²¹ Davidson RL, Weber RJ, Liu H2, Sharma-Oates A, and Viant MR. “Galaxy-M: a Galaxy workflow for processing and analyzing direct infusion and liquid chromatography mass spectrometry-based metabolomics data”. *Gigascience*. 2016 Feb 23;5:10. doi: 10.1186/s13742-016-0115-8.

²² www.openms.de/

Figure 6. Workshop/hackathon about Galaxy organized at CEA.

As part of its objective to raise community awareness and establish close links with the Metabolomics and biomedical community, the PhenoMeNal consortium organised a workshop on **Computational Workflows and Workflow engines**²³ at the Metabolomics Conference 2016, Dublin. The workshop was hosted in collaboration with the Metabolomics community Prof. Mark Viant, Ralf Weber and Warwick Dunn. The session included a series of talks on platforms such as Workflow4Metabolomics, MassCascade-KNIME²⁴, Galaxy-M, MetaboAnalyst²⁵, PhenoMeNal and MetaSpace²⁶ projects followed by discussions on the current shortcomings and improvements that could help widen the adoption of these type of tools within the metabolomics community.

²³ <http://metabolomics2016.org/images/2016-Metabolomics-Workshop-Detailed-Overview-5-24-16.pdf>

²⁴ <https://bitbucket.org/sbeisken/masscascadeknime/wiki/installation>

²⁵ <http://www.metaboanalyst.ca>

²⁶ <http://metaspace2020.eu>

Workshop Session 6: Computational Workflows and Workflow Engines

Organisers: Mark Viant, Ralf Weber, Warwick Dunn, Pablo Moreno, Reza Salek, Christoph Steinbeck and the PhenoMeNal consortium

Computational analysis of high-dimensional and high-volume metabolomics data is a complex, time-consuming process including many steps, some of which are still the focus of intense research. Workflow management environments applied in metabolomics and cross-omics analyses are therefore an essential requirement to allow standardisation of bioinformatics analysis, provide access to the metabolomics community, and produce high-quality, reproducible results in a time-effective manner. A few open-source workflows have recently been applied in different environments including Galaxy-M, Workflow4Metabolomics, MetaDB and MetaboAnalyst. This workshop will address, in talks and discussions, the growing need for the international metabolomics community to understand the current availability workflows and capabilities of these environments.

Figure 7 Workshop at Metabolomics 2016

The partners also presented the project on several occasions as part of the dissemination activities.

Date and location	Event/URL	Type of audience	Contribution	Attendee
3rd March, 2016, Cambridge	Visit to the Tony Vidal-Puig Lab at the Institute of Metabolic Sciences (IMS).	Experimentalists working in Metabolomics	Presentation	Pablo Moreno, Christoph Steinbeck (EMBL-EBI)
14th-16th March 2016, Paris	The Workflow4Metabolomics infrastructure, the Galaxy environment, and the PhenoMeNal project	Developers	Presentation and hackathon	Workflow4Metabolomics, PhenoMeNal, Galaxy-M
27th May 2016, Barcelona	Metabolic phenotyping in clinical practice	Clinicians, industry, metabolomics experts, ethicist and PhenoMeNal consortium	Presentation	Christoph Steinbeck (EMBL-EBI)
9th June 2016,	Research	Researchers,	Presentation	Kristian

Martin-Luther Halle University	Seminar	Academic institutions		Peters (IPB)
29th May - 3rd June 2016, Ascona	Non-target screening of organic chemicals for a comprehensive environmental risk assessment: http://www.nontarget2016.ch/index.php	Academic institutions, industry and regulatory bodies	Presentation	Steffen Neumann (IPB)
3rd - 7th July 2016, Aarhus Denmark	EUROMAR 2016, http://www.euromar2016.org/index.php	Academic institutions, industry	Presentation	Claudio Luchinat (CIRMMP)
18-20 April, 2016, Ghent Belgium	PSI Spring Workshop	Academic institutions	Presentation	Reza Salek (EMBL-EBI)
22nd April 2016, Peking	Xing Da Lecture, College of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering (CCME) of Peking University	Academic institutions	Presentation	Claudio Luchinat (CIRMMP)
17th -19th May 2016, Nice	Biobanking National Infrastructure Meeting ²⁷	Researchers from European and Asian biobanks	Presentation	Paola Turano (CIRMMP)
6th -10th June, Barcelona	CAC 2016, http://www.cacbarcelona.com	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Poster	Alberto Pasamontes, University of Leiden (UL)
27th - 30th June	Metabolomics	Academic	Posters	Kim Kultima,

²⁷ <http://unspod.unice.fr/video/4128-paola-turano-biobanques/>

2016, Dublin	2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	institutions, researchers, industry		Stephanie Herman (UU)
27th-30th June 2016, Dublin	Metabolomics 2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Workshop presentations: Computational workflow and workflow engines and metaRbolomics: The R toolbox for Metabolomics	Etienne Thévenot (CEA)
27th-30th June 2016, Dublin	Metabolomics 2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Workshop in Computational workflow and workflow engines and data standards in Metabolomics	Reza Salek (EMBL-EBI)
27th - 30th June 2016, Dublin	Metabolomics 2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Poster	Roger Mallol (SIB)

Mon 18th Jul 2016, 15:00 – 16:00	CDISC Pharmacogenomics Working Group	IMI eTRIKS representative (Academics and Industry) and CDISC working group	Working Group Presentation	Philippe Rocca-Serra- University of Oxford
27th - 30th June 2016, Dublin	Metabolomics 2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Presentation	Tim Ebbels (ICL)
27th - 30th June 2016, Dublin	Metabolomics 2016, http://metabolomics2016.org	Academic institutions, researchers, industry	Poster	Jake Pearce (ICL)
March 2016, Stevenage, UK	Physchem Forum, GlaxoSmithKline,	Scientists	Presentation	Robert Glen (ICL)
May 2016, ICL	CSM seminar	Researchers	Presentation	Noureddin Sadawi, Jianliang Gao (ICL)
April, 2016, London	HPRU (Health Protection Research Unit in Health Impact of Environmental Hazards) Annual	Academic institutions	Presentation	Ibrahim Karaman (ICL)

	Meeting			
27th June 2016, Strasbourg	Cheminformatics Summer School	Academic institutions	Presentation	Robert Glen (ICL)
June 2016, London	Imperial College London	Researchers	Short Courses (Hands on Data Analysis for Metabolic Profiling and Metabolic Profiling in Health and Disease)	Tim Ebbels (ICL)
July 2016, London	ITMAT group meeting	Researchers	Presentation	Jianliang Gao (ICL)

Table 3. List of events with PhenoMeNal participation

The project was also disseminated through meetings with other relevant projects and e-infrastructures, publications, social media and blog posts on project and other scientific websites:

- i. June 23rd, 2016: ‘Stable Isotope Resolved Metabolomics’ meeting. Following up on a COSMOS meeting held in Barcelona in April 2015 and taking advantage of the presence of Dr Teresa Fan as part of the scientific advisory board, Dr Cascante, Dr Pedro Aauri Carulla, Dr Rocca-Serra, Dr Salek met to refine the specifications of annotation requirements and data matrix structure to report isotologue distributions resulting from SIRM experiments.
- ii. July 3-5th 2016. Meeting in EMBL-EBI with Dr Saravanan Dayalan, from Metabolomics Australia, author of MasTR-MS, a LIMS system for mass spectrometry based Metabolomics. Discussion mzTab standards and exporting data from MasTR-MS LIMS into MetaboLights
- iii. July 6th 2016. Meeting in Oxford with Dr Saravanan Dayalan, from Metabolomics Australia, author of MasTR-MS, a LIMS system for mass spectrometry based Metabolomics. Discussion and plan for finalizing ISA-Tab export from MasTR-MS. Decision to rely on MasTR-MS “sample class” to generate a correct ISA-Tab Study Sample file, ensuring the correct number of sample is generated. Creation of a dedicated slack channel for future and follow-up discussion.
- iv. July 12th, 2016. ISA meeting in Oxford with Imperial College: Attendees: Jack Pearce, Ibrahim Karaman, Nouredin Sadawi, Tim Ebbels, Jianliang Gao, Jazz Mac-Smith, David Johnson, Alejandra Gonzalez-Beltran, Philippe Rocca-Serra
- v. Virtual Research Environments for Clinical Metabolomics²⁸, SNIC Science Cloud, 2016-04-20.
- vi. GigaBlog: Building a PhenoMeNal metabolomics e-infrastructure²⁹
- vii. Meeting report entitled "Quality Matters -2016 Annual conference of the National Infrastructures for biobanking", accepted by *Biopreservation and Biobanking*.
- viii. “Entropy-Based Network Representation of the Individual Metabolic Phenotype” Edoardo Saccenti, Giulia Menichetti, Veronica Ghini, Daniel Remondini, Leonardo Tenori, and Claudio Luchinat, *J. Proteome Res.*, Article ASAP, DOI: 10.1021/acs.jproteome.6b00454
- ix. National Phenome Centre Scientific Advisory Board, April 2016, Robert Glen, Imperial College London.

²⁸ <https://cloud.snic.se/index.php/2016/04/20/virtual-research-environments-for-clinical-metabolomics/>

²⁹ <http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/gigablog/2016/07/19/guest-posting-building-phenomenal-metabolomics-e-infrastructure/>

- x. Manuscript titled “A Workflow For Integrated Processing of Multi-Cohort Untargeted 1H NMR Metabolomics Data In Large Scale Metabolic Epidemiology” is under review after major revision at the Journal of Proteome Research.
- xi. Paper: “Power Analysis and sample Size Determination in Metabolic Phenotyping”, Blaise et al., DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.6b00188 Anal. Chem. 2016, 88, 5179–5188
- xii. Blog posts and publications on project website³⁰
- xiii. YouTube:
 - a. NMR in Metabolomics³¹
 - b. Video interview with Paola Turano³²
- xiv. Created and committed changes to several projects in PhenoMeNal github³³ and jenkins³⁴

Task 3.4 PhenoMeNal will also build an intensive dialog between mass spectroscopy and NMR instrument vendors, search engine providers, experimentalists, data resources, and publishers

The consortium worked together to compile a list of potential stakeholders to explore possible synergies and liaison activities for continued sustainability of the project beyond the initial funding period. An **annual stakeholder meeting** was organised on 14th June 2016 that brought together 11 stakeholders from diverse communities including industry, metabolomics laboratories, systems biology and bioethics. The prime focus was to discuss some of the pressing challenges facing the biomedical community; handling of extreme data volumes in molecular phenotyping, analysis of metabolomics data sets in conjunction with the genomic data, transmission of these large datasets in convenient time frames between institutions and data privacy and ethics. This was an exclusive opportunity to share, exchange views, identify solutions and discuss ways to enable strong collaboration for the future.

³⁰ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/home/>

³¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=COBGJWahU_4

³² <https://vimeo.com/170821543>

³³ <https://github.com/phnmnl/>

³⁴ <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>

Figure 7 Twitter feed - PhenoMeNal stakeholder meeting

The main objectives laid out for the meeting were:

- To identify key challenges in the processing and analysis of metabolomics/other omics data
- Data sharing, privacy and ethics issues in case of human data
- Usability of an e-infrastructure like PhenoMeNal in addressing these challenges

The event was designed to be a synergistic workspace with presentations and group discussions on predecided themes and topics. The participants were asked to prepare a 20 minutes presentation covering the following points:

- A description of work in relation to clinical metabolomics
- Views on metabolomics data management and processing in broader context of an infrastructure like PhenoMeNal
- Challenges met by your organisation/institution in this respect
- Vision on the possible solutions

The meeting created a platform for the PhenoMeNal and its stakeholders to exchange information on needs for:

- Data standards and models
- Data complexity and volume
- ELSI requirements for sensitive data and protecting patient rights
- Data protection laws
- Computational challenges
- Principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) data
- Possible solutions provided by PhenoMeNal to address above issues

The PhenoMeNal consortium plans to take into account the rich outcomes of this meeting in defining the planning and progress of its current and future work. For a detailed report on Stakeholder meeting see deliverable **D3.1.1 Report on the annual stakeholder meeting**.

The PhenoMeNal consortium also hosted its first **Industry workshop on 28th June 2016** in Dublin. The aim of the meeting was to create a lasting interaction with industry, in order to raise awareness of the PhenoMeNal initiative and to ensure optimal interoperability of PhenoMeNal infrastructure and instrument vendor's data formats and tools. The vendors who participated in this workshop were:

- Metabolomics Discoveries
- Sciex
- Shimadzu
- Bruker
- Waters

The participants were asked to **nominate a person for the PhenoMeNal Industry Panel**. This Industry panel will be a sounding board for the consortium, and be consulted at least once a year on the development of the e-infrastructure. The current members (at the time of writing of this report) of this panel include:

- Martin Buratti, Biocrates
- Michael Rodamer, Agilent Technologies
- Robert Tonge, Waters

Future Plans:

- Production of web-based tutorials on the project website

WP4 – Interfacing with Biomedical European Infrastructures

WP leader: Consorzio Interuniversitario Risonanze Magnetiche di Metallo Proteine (CIRMMP)

This work package is focussed on fostering interactions between PhenoMeNal and its potential large users and/or future partners.

The main achievements of this reporting period are:

- Established communications with the other European Infrastructures and relevant projects and align PhenoMeNal activities to the requirements of such infrastructures and centres.
- Increased synergies between projects by providing input and receiving feedback from working groups addressing activities of common interest.
- Establishment of working group

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period:

Task 4.1 Collecting and reporting on the requirements of research and/or industry centers that produce or make use of metabolomics (possibly together with other -omics techniques) data

A short questionnaire, based on input from all partners, to collect an initial overview of requirements by national/regional research centers, large infrastructures, and other major initiatives making use of metabolomics, was developed by CIRMMP. The questionnaire addressed the following topics:

- Type of e-infrastructure
- Computational requirements
- Storage requirements
- Data throughput
- Software requirements

All partners provided contacts to send the questionnaire to and/or circulated the questionnaire themselves. To facilitate the respondents, we provided both a doc file and an online survey on SurveyMonkey (<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/YNTVTCJ>).

Problems and challenges encountered

Because the survey was made available after mid-June, there has been a slow response from some contacts, due to holidays. We decided to leave it open past the due date of D4.1 to continue to receive input and eventually update the report after M12.

Task 4.2 Establish and convene working groups involving the PhenoMeNal consortium as well as participants in other biomedical infrastructure and research projects.

The consortium tried to leverage the contacts initially established on the occasion of a meeting with members of the CORBEL consortium organized by the CIRMMMP partner in Florence (February 2016). A consensus document based on the discussion at the meeting was finalized during the current reporting period (included as an appendix to the updated D2.1). After that, we sought interactions mainly with the ISBE ESFRI Infrastructure, also because of both the more clear scientific case for metabolomics in the activities of ISBE and the comments received at the 6-month review by the EC. To this end, we involved one of the WP leaders of ISBE (University of Wageningen) in the stakeholder meeting held on the occasion of the annual meeting (see agenda in the section on WP1). After the discussions held on this occasion, involving various partners, it was agreed that one delegate of PhenoMeNal (WP4 leader) would spend a two-day scouting visit at the University of Wageningen in order to prepare a first draft of a position/perspective document on the role of metabolomics in systems biology and the associated computational needs. The document will provide input to PhenoMeNal on a potentially very relevant area of application of metabolomics and other omics. The implementation of the group working on the document achieves **MS4.1**.

Future Plans

- Closer interaction of the networking work packages (WP2, WP3, WP4) together with management (WP1), by having separate hangouts of the PIs and key staff involved in these WPs. The objective is to maximize synergies.

WP5 – Operations and maintenance of PhenoMeNa GRID/CLOUD

WP Leader: Uppsala University

This work package is focussed on the PhenoMeNa e-infrastructure underlying the PhenoMeNa Virtual Research Environments (VRE). End users, such as researchers and research teams, educators, SMEs, and any other type of user, will be able to on-demand and through a simple user interface create an environment of tools, services, data supporting their research needs. Hardware setup and software deployment required to operate these facilities are completely transparent to the VRE and hence the users can focus on the analysis and not the plumbing (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Responsibilities when carrying out contemporary metabolomics data analysis.

(Left:) Today's situation: Scientists are responsible for everything, including the computer hardware, installing all necessary software, and carrying out the actual analysis. All execution is limited by the resources in the single computer.

(Right:) The PhenoMeNa approach: Software tools are available as containers without the need for installations, with data in agreed-upon interoperable file formats. The VRE can be started on single computers or on cloud resources, and the scientists benefit from only needing to deal with the analysis as the technical implementations are handled by the VRE.

The main achievements of the reporting period are:

- Continuous Integration system with initial services
- Achievement of a proof-of-concept integrations between VMIs

A summary of the progress of work in this reporting period is:

A) Continuous Integration system with initial services

See Task 5.5 below.

B) Proof-of-concept integrations between VMIs

The PhenoMeNal VRE has reached beta-stage where proof-of-concept integrations between VMIs and containers is operational, and where initial services makes it possible to carry out pieces of analysis workflows within the VRE. Seven demonstrators have been developed to demonstrate the integration:

- R-based metabolomics workflow:** Services were containerized and a Jupyter notebook developed, demonstrating that an R-based metabolomics workflow from the Kultima group (<http://www.caramba.clinic/>) could be executed within PhenoMeNal VRE
- Fluxomics Tools:** Two workflows for the study of metabolic networks based on ¹³C-tracer mass spectrometry were developed and integrated into PhenoMeNal VRE; a) Stationary-state fluxomics, and b) Dynamic fluxomics.
- Statistical analysis of the sacurine data set:** Reproducing a workflow for characterization of the physiological variations of the metabolome in biofluids within PhenoMeNal VRE.
- Isotopologue Parameter Optimization (IPO):** We implemented a workflow for automated optimization of XCMS parameters for LC-MS for peak picking and retention time correction; a computationally intensive task that was demonstrated within PhenoMeNal VRE.
- MS-Convert:** A tool for conversion from a MS RAW vendor data format to mzML was demonstrated on data from Bruker instruments, with results visualized within PhenoMeNal VRE.
- nmrML-Conversion:** Integration and demonstration of Open Source converter nmrmlconv on part data from the NMR Mus musculus data set within PhenoMeNal VRE.
- Bayesian AuTomed Metabolite Analyser for NMR spectra (BATMAN NMR):** A workflow containing the computationally demanding tool BATMAN for NMR data analysis was demonstrated within the PhenoMeNal VRE.

This task was reported as deliverable **D5.2**.

Task 5.1 Operations and maintenance of the GRID/Cloud Infrastructure

In T5.1 all partners will contribute to the operation and upgrade of the middleware and the other necessary software tools that are needed to keep the GRID/cloud infrastructure and related functionalities fully available to users. PhenoMeNal sites have been established at UU and EBI on OpenStack, and also demonstrated and used on Google Cloud Platform (GCP) and Amazon EC2. Work is ongoing to set up a PhenoMeNal site at partner ICL. A large part of the work has been dedicated for developing contextualization scripts and to work with frameworks for microservice architecture VRE deployment on the various platforms. This task was reported in D5.2.

T5.2: Operation and Maintenance of the PhenoMeNal VRC

In T5.2 the PhenoMeNal VRC (gateway/portal) will be installed, maintained operational and continuously improved as new relevant technologies and tools will become available. During the period, the foundation for the portal in terms of underlying architecture and design has been researched together with WP6 and WP9 and driven the VRE user interface design.

T5.3: Provisioning of the PhenoMeNal Services

T5.3 covers the installation, operation and maintenance of services (e.g. as deployed publicly accessible VMIs) and other types of services to be deployed on the project grid/cloud. The work in this task has focused on researching, demonstrating, testing technologies, and educating PhenoMeNal developers on microservice-based containerized service development and -integration. Docker has been chosen as container technology, and together with WP9 the packaging of containerized tools have been implemented in PhenoMeNal continuous integration system (see T5.5 below). This task was reported in D5.2.

T5.4: Operation and Maintenance of a reference site for analysis on private data

T5.4 entails maintaining an operational reference infrastructure for operating with PhenoMeNal services on sensitive (private) data. The setup of a site for private analysis at ICL has been initiated and will be continued during the next year.

Task 5.5 Operation and maintenance of Continuous Integration System

PhenoMeNal has deployed a Continuous Integration (CI) (Jenkins) instance³⁵ as a focal point of PhenoMeNal development to gather the building of all tools, package them into virtual machines or software containers, carry out unit testing, and publish the

³⁵ <https://phenomenal-h2020.eu/jenkins/>

components to public repositories and dedicated PhenoMeNal repositories. The Jenkins instance comprised as of 2016-08-27 40 builds (projects) and 26 members of the consortium registered; this list will grow further during the project lifetime. In order to tighten security, a two-factor authentication mechanism was added. This task was reported as deliverable **D5.1**.

Problems and challenges encountered

Contextualization, which comprises the launching and configuration of compute nodes on an IaaS provider (such as OpenStack, Google Cloud etc) currently takes about 30 minutes to complete. We consider this to be too long and will work to speed up this process. Also, Docker images can become very heavy relatively quickly, for which we have been slowly documenting and enforcing more good practices to avoid this. Large Docker images also makes deployment to the container orchestrator slower; again, another reason for improving the quality of our Docker images.

License issues of DLLs required for RAW formats conversions. Converting to open formats normally requires usage of proprietary libraries written by the vendors that have restrictive licenses, which makes it problematic for open redistribution in the form of Docker containers. One solution is to host these particular containers in a closed private Docker registry (password protected), and then add the adequate secret to the container orchestrator cluster to be able to pull these images. We will continue to investigate the best solution for this situation.

Future Plans

- Working towards producing and improving internal and external documentation regarding development, deployment, security of the VRE and its components. The main documentation platform is the PhenoMeNal wiki
- Establish e-Infrastructure tests on Jenkins for VRE contextualization and for ensuring running instances are operational.
- Work on improving the speed for VRE contextualization using e.g. pre-packaged VMIs, as well as resolving technical issues for service GUIs and workflow engines Galaxy and Jupyter.
- With respect to compute and data federation, we plan to initiate this task in M13 and the rough plan is to investigate data federation using iRODS, distributed container orchestration in Kubernetes, the new Pachyderm system for containerized analytics, and the use of Apache Spark for multi-data center analysis.
- To demonstrate scalability of PhenoMeNal VRE (after its deployment) by reproducing one or more large-scale studies.

WP6 – PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway

WP leader: European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL-EBI)

The main achievements during this period are:

- 2nd UX workshop to ensure that the VRC is designed to suite the users
- PhenoMeNal VRC (static) portal publicly available.
- Online user feedback form.

A summary of the progress of the work in this reporting period:

Task 6.2 Deployment of the PhenoMeNal VRC

The PhenoMeNal VRE Portal is the entry point (gateway) to all the tools and workflows on offer. The VRE Portal is available at <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu/portal/>, and in the short term will empower users to deploy their own PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Environments (VREs) on private and public cloud providers, as well as provide documentation for deployments on local hardware. Most of the tools are accessible through the Galaxy workflow environment, and in the future, through command line alternatives like Jupyter/iPython. All the tools in the workflow environment have been deployed as Docker containers, to fully modularise the architecture, and we also make them available as such.

Problems and challenges encountered

During our latest UX testing, the test users did not really understand, nor trust, the term “Virtual” in VRE. So to make this more clear we have chosen to externally brand the portal as “PhenoMeNal Cloud Research Environment Portal”. This improved the trust issues we experienced in the first round of testing and apparently made more sense to test users. Further in this document, VRE Portal is used as the descriptive term.

Cloud Research Environment

How does it work?

You follow our easy setup process and install the Cloud Research Environment (CRE) on the PhenoMeNa cloud or you can use your own cloud provider such as Amazon Cloud, Google Cloud etc.

● ○ ○ ○

All your favourite metabolomics analysis applications under one hood accessible through Open Source scientific web environments, Galaxy Workflow and Jupyter IPython coding environment

Test drive our Cloud Research Environment

[Galaxy Workflow](#) or [Jupyter IPython](#)

Note that this is a public instance accessible by everyone

Want to give it a go?

[Create Cloud Research Environment](#)

Do you like the idea but need a local installation of the CRE?

Don't worry, we have a solution for you too. We can provide you with all the kit for a local installation of our Cloud Research Environment. This approach is more work for you but you will have the benefit of having all the apps on our App Library available locally.

[Find out more about local installation](#)

You can install all the applications in our App Library locally.

You can install the whole Cloud Research Environment including our App Library locally.

Access to all the standard Cloud providers or own free PhenoMeNa cloud

Don't know much about Cloud providers but want to use our CRE? Don't worry. Our default setup process is easy to use and will get you started in no time

Figure 10. PhenoMeNa VRE Portal initial deployment page, where the user can choose from a Cloud deployment (upper fold) or installation on local hardware (middle)

fold). For the unconvinced user, the page presents a link to the test-drive installation (upper fold), to improve the understanding of what could be possible with a deployed VRE for the user.

Cloud Research Environment / Local Installation

All applications in the App Library run within the Cloud Research Environment on your local computer(s).

Access to your local installation of the CRE is through Open Source scientific web environments such as Galaxy or Jupyter.

Your local installation of the CRE can be run as virtual machines or if you have administration rights directly on the computers

Install your local Cloud Research Environment

What will I need to run a local installation of the CRE?

Not much is the easy answer and we can guide you through it step-by-step

Installation Requirements

A local installation of a free virtual machine environment (Virtual Box) or administration rights on the host computer(s).

Our CRE can run on most Operating Systems.

This solution specifically caters for clinical metabolomics where local installations are driven by the demands of the hospital IT requirements.

Local installations still benefit from all the applications in the App Library but are run on your local network.

A local installation of our CRE is ideal if you need to keep your data locally due to privacy and security

Figure 11. PhenoMeNal VRE Portal page for local installation of the PhenoMeNal VRE

App Library

App Library showcases all applications that are available via Galaxy workflows and Jupyter libraries through the Cloud Research Environment.

Search for Apps **Go**

- Metabolomic Technology ⓘ
 - DAD
 - DIMS
 - GC-MS
 - LC-MS
 - NMR
 - RAMAN
- Data analysis ⓘ
 - Annotation
 - Normalisation
 - Processing
 - Statistical Analysis

BATMAN NMR

Docker container produced by PhenoMeNal H2020 consortium for BATMAN NMR

PhenoMeNal MANTL

PhenoMeNal MANTL

W4M biosigner

Discovery of significant signatures from omics data

Figure 12. PhenoMeNal VRE App Library

User feedback is one of the most important ways to improve user satisfaction and ensure our offering is fit for purpose. Just collecting feedback does not make our users more satisfied; we need to make sure our users feel the benefit of their feedback. Together with the current on-going User Experience (UX) activities, in addition to the extensive UX work already carried out in D6.1 (User Experience Document on VRC Design Guide), user feedback will continue to be very important in our future development. We specifically acknowledge the importance of structured user feedback forms, i.e. capturing categories of issues and priority indicators, in order to efficiently delegate issues to the experts most suitable to tackle a specific user problem in a timely manner.

The PhenoMeNal consortia now has an effective sustainable feedback tool (see figure 13) that enables us to act upon requests in a personalised manner. In addition, by

integrating WP Support Plus feedback forms with our Pivotal Tracker project management tool we can rapidly allocate suitable consortia users to deal with the request as they happen.

[Tickets](#) [Create New Ticket](#) [FAQs](#)

Create New Ticket

Subject *

Description *

B I U S x_2 x^2 I_x

Styles Format Font Size Source

Category *

Priority *

Attachments
 no files selected

Figure 13. User feedback form

Future Plans

- Development includes the development of online installation of VRE Portal. The VRE Portal is, according to plans, currently partly static. Later deployments will see a fully functional VRE portal and a larger number of available tools.

WP7 - Privacy and Ethics

WP leader: Imperial College London (ICL)

The main achievements during the reporting are:

- Development of appropriate policies and procedures for compliance with ELSI.
- Ethical approvals for use of test data sets within PhenoMeNal was achieved.

A summary of the progress of work in the reporting period:

Task 7.4 Evaluate the introduction of a data provider form to be completed by each data provider to the project, the intention of which is to ensure that all ethical aspects of making data available within PhenoMeNal have been addressed, similarly to what implemented in the BioMedBridges³⁶ project.

Research data derived from patient samples is sensitive and subject to Ethical, Legal and Social Implications (ELSI). Submitting such data for use and subsequent re-use thus requires consideration of ELSI regulations. In order to enforce patient rights and maximise the opportunities for research, guide users, and, comply with local and international laws and ethical considerations, a data provider form provides the rigour required to consider the implications of acquiring, donating and using clinically derived data as well as being a record of the conditions under which the data are made available. A guidance document on handling sensitive human data was produced. Technical solutions to secure deposition and access of data were explored, using the exemplar of the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA)³⁷. The details can be found in deliverable **D7.3 Evaluation report for the introduction of a data provider form**.

³⁶ <http://www.biomedbridges.eu>

³⁷ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ega/home>

Task 7.5 Develop processes in collaboration with BBMRI and Biomedbridges to extract maximum information from sensitive datasets with minimum compromise within legal, ethical and privacy constraints.

Based on the principles and framework resulting from the two ELSI workshops, and in discussion with experts from BiomedBridges (and our expert collaborators in the ELSI area), we have designed a process to enable the user to access Phenomenal resources, with proper consideration of ELSI requirements. The process is exemplified by two workflows. The first workflow is aimed at users who bring their own data and process it with Phenomenal tools. The second workflow addresses the needs of users who access data from repositories through the PhenoMeNal portal, and then (optionally) process it using Phenomenal tools. Both workflows address issues such as terms of use, data access agreements and anonymisation. These have been codified into an html form exemplifying how the process could be implemented within the Phenomenal infrastructure. Details can be found in deliverable **D7.4 Process to extract maximum information from sensitive datasets with minimum compromise, in collaboration with BBMRI and BioMedBridges.**

Task 7.6 Identify human clinical datasets to test drive development and ensure that the ethical approvals cover use within the PhenoMeNal project, including the non-EC partner SIB. Provide EC/REA with copies of ethical approvals and related informed consent forms and information material for patients.

In order to create the projected data processing pipeline and for testing our ethical, legal and social implications (ELSI) goals, we need to use data sets that closely mimic the types of data which will be analysed by our future users. We have evaluated the associated documentation for each dataset. In particular, where data is not open and freely available, we have obtained ethical approval documentation, patient information and patient permission forms. Some data will only be used at the host institution, where ethical approval for use at that institution is present. Open data (from a public repository such as MetaboLights data, <http://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>) can be freely used within the terms of use of the repository. Details can be found in deliverable **D7.5 Report to EC/REA with ethical approvals, informed consent forms and patient information material of datasets to be used within PhenoMeNal e-infrastructure development.**

Future Plans

- Continue to raise awareness of information management within the consortium and user community
- Ensure on-going ELSI compliance from all partners across all WPs.

WP8 – Data provenance, compliance and Integrity

WP leader: The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford (UOXF)

The main achievements during this reporting period are:

- Completion of receipt of contributions to the survey on ‘Standards, Compliance and Data Integrity’. At the time of writing of this deliverable from WP8, the relevant deliverable D8.1 that reports on the standards survey results is being finalized. The full results of the survey analysis are documented in that deliverable report (D8.1).
- Work towards modularization of the ISA data formats has begun and progressed well with the development of the ISA API providing key functionalities such as interconversion between Tab delimited and JSON formats, native python syntactic validation, programmatic creation of ISA documents. Extensive testing is underway as well as development of methods for native conversion from Metabolomics Workbench and Biocrates metadata format to ISA for integration with PhenoMenal data analysis tools.
- Expansion of nmrML data standard to increase coverage and adjustments for Galaxy workflow support have been done
- Containerization of data standards support tools has been archived.

A summary of the progress of work in this reporting period:

Task 8.1 Use cases and state of the art of communication standards

A **Data Standards Survey** was initiated to address the project’s objective to first obtain an overview of the relevant data exchange and storage standards in use, then, to assess the level of awareness about existing standardization initiative and finally to identify any gaps in coverage which PhenoMenal would have to address. This review also aimed to identify areas to improve and scale up tools to ensure efficient integration and workflow crosstalk (see Deliverable 8.1 for further detail). Modularization of the ISA

formats and expansion of nmrML works towards upcoming milestones and deliverables in Year 2, while the containerization of standards tools goes towards adoption of data standards tooling and cross-package activity with WP9. All of this activity is informed by the results of contributions from the metabolomics community via the WP8 survey.

The survey, at the time of writing, has gathered 135 responses, through dissemination of the PhenoMeNal consortium's research network contacts, as well as public dissemination via social media (Twitter, LinkedIn groups³⁸ as well as the PhenoMeNal blog), the Metabolomics Society (via the MetaboNews newsletter as well as a dedicated email sent to all MetSoc members) and support from two leading data journals, GigaScience (by giving PhenoMeNal a guest blog post³⁹) and Nature Scientific Data (by promoting the aforementioned guest blog post, as well as actively using their social media presence to garner responses to the survey).

TASK GROUPS CORNER **Data Standards Task Group**

General Announcements for related standards activities:

Metabolomics Data Infrastructures Survey

The PhenoMeNal project is developing an open-source e-infrastructure for the processing, analysis, and information-mining of medical molecular phenotyping and genotyping data that will be generated by metabolomics applications. The project is publicly funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme. For more information, please see <http://phenomenal-h2020.eu>

To gain a better understanding of the requirements for data infrastructures for metabolomics research, PhenoMeNal has commissioned a survey to gain insight into current practices, future needs, and opinions, on how metabolomics research data is managed, published, and disseminated. We would be grateful if you could contribute to the survey at the link below.

Survey link: <https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/metabolomics-data>

Contact:

David Johnson (david.johnson@oerc.ox.ac.uk)

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Figure 14. MetaboNews⁴⁰ featuring the PhenoMeNal Data standards Survey

³⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2660384/>, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/1790449>,
<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/2206472>, <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/159027>

³⁹ <http://blogs.biomedcentral.com/gigablog/2016/07/19/guest-posting-building-phenomenal-metabolomics-e-infrastructure/>

⁴⁰ http://www.metabonews.ca/Mar2016/MetaboNews_Mar2016.htm

Figure 15. Twitter feed from Nature Scientific Data

Task 8.2 Standards for exchanging experimental and clinical metadata

Modularization of data formats

At UOXF, the ISA API is being developed to enable programmatic access to existing ISA tab metadata, as well as facilities to modify and create ISA metadata to aid in managing metabolomics data, as well as supporting the entire workflow from wet-lab through data analysis to data publication. ISA is being developed to enable FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data objects, which is key to preserving the long-term value of data generated by PhenoMeNal clinical partners.

Expansion of NMR data standards

At the IPB the nmrML data standard was expanded to capture quantification and peak assignments as well as standardized processing methods to cover open source tools

like nmrAssign and NMRProcFlow. The nmrCV was expanded to increase coverage on processing parameter descriptors for the mentioned tools. An initial draft of a metabolite identification ontology (MIECO) was created to cover high level metabolite evidence descriptors for NMR, MS, UV and IR spectroscopy.

In all tasks, the WP8 partners are working together towards achieving the work package milestones, as well as ensuring uptake of data standards across data-contributing sites. A WP8 Google Hangout was held on June 7th 2016 to touch base on progress across the partners in WP8 and to update on survey progress and ask for further help with disseminating the survey. The NMR Working Group held a Google Hangout on June 24th 2016. Apart from the consortium meetings held in Rhodes that WP8 participating partners were all represented at, a face-to-face was organised between UOXF and ICL in order to aid with and plan out adoption of ISA standards in the National Phenome Centre at Imperial College, as well as to begin work on putting describing the MESA dataset with ISA metadata.

Future Plans

- Work towards deliverables:
 - **D8.3 “nmrML, mzML data exchange formats and associated terminologies for instrument raw, with reference implementation guidelines and validation rules”** at M18.
 - **D8.2 “Modularized ISA model and format: biospecimen centric schema, corresponding xml schemas, reference implementation guidelines and validation rules”** at M24.
- The reference implementations and tooling underway in collaboration with WP9.

WP9 – Tools, workflows, audit and data management

WP leader: Leibniz Institute of Plant Biochemistry (IPB)

During this period the main achievements were:

- Containerisation (Virtual Machine Images) of the following Preprocess Tools:
 - msconvert as part of ProteoWizard (“docker-pwiz”)
 - nmrMLconv as part of the nmrML workflow (“docker-nmrmlconv”)
 - compassXport as part of inhouse tool of third-party vendor Bruker (“docker-compassxport”)

The containerisation of these preprocessing tools is the first crucial step that all the workflows depend on, as the conversion into open source community standards and formats allows to further process the data in a vendor-agnostic manner. These activities correspond to the consortium's initiative towards the project's objective. Work is also underway to finish the upcoming deliverables D9.2.2 Data VM and D9.2.3 Services VM.

A summary of the progress of work in this reporting period:

Task 9.1 Data processing pipelines

The goal in WP9 is to develop and maintain the primary scientific and technological tools as well as corresponding interfaces. We specify and integrate software pipelines and tools utilised in the PhenoMeNal e-Infrastructure into Containers or Virtual Machine Images (VMI), adhering to data standards developed in WP8 and supporting the interoperability and federation middleware developed in WP5.

We have successfully provided first builds of Preprocess VMIs of tools that convert raw LC/MS and NMR data into open standard formats (mzML and nmrML). These Preprocess VMIs stand at the very beginning on which all the other tools and workflows depend on (see D9.2.1 report). We used public repositories (github.com) and continuous integration to always provide development snapshots of the infrastructure VMIs. In order to avoid data lock-in and ensure continuous availability of the infrastructure we are closely working together with WP8 and WP5. A primary goal is to hide the complexity of the underlying infrastructure to the actual user (e.g. biologists, clinicians), while giving easy-to-understand technical instructions to bioinformaticians for installing the supplied PhenoMeNal VMIs in a short time while preserving data privacy and security. In order to reach these goals, we already began integrating our tools into the Galaxy framework and Workflow4Metabolomics. We also performed extensive testing with the underlying infrastructure together with WP5 (Kubernetes local cloud environment). As such, we used the available LC/MS data set from the Sacurine use case⁴¹ to perform initial testing. We also wrote two blog posts to encourage developers to bring their tools to PhenoMeNal and participated to the PhenoMeNal H2020 wiki⁴² (see outreach activity here in the D1.4.2 report). To establish best practices, ICL, EBI and IPB worked together on containerizing the BATMAN NMR tool⁴³, and set up technical guidelines for the PhenoMeNal consortium and extended the list of tools that need to be containerised for later packaging into VMIs and began with containerising

⁴¹ http://workflow4metabolomics.org/dataset_sacurine

⁴² <https://github.com/phnmnl/phenomenal-h2020/wiki>

⁴³ <https://github.com/phnmnl/docker-batman>

them (in preparation for the next D9.2.3). We began working on container streamlining, testing and statistics and defining short-living job (“tools”) and bringing long-living services (“Galaxy as-a-service”) into the PhenoMeNal cloud e-infrastructure.

We arranged for 6 hangouts (with usually 10-15 attendees each) during the period so far:

- WP5 Hangout 2016-03-17: Development pipeline. Deployment guides.
- WP9 Hangout 2016-04-05: Nail down Use Cases and first efforts for integration. Response of the Call for data and prototypes. Extending the list of tools that need to be containerised (produce VMIs). Defining tool jobs.
- WP20 Hangout 2016-05-03: Coordinate how WP5 and WP9 feed into WP6. How tools and workflows integrate into VRE and which underlying tools/techniques must be used.
- WP20 Hangout 2016-05-20: VRE mockup status and integration into WP9. Defining 5 initial use cases supported and workflows on them. Agreed on writing tutorials and supplying tech demos.
- WP20 Hangout 2016-06-03: Contribution to Galaxy and Workflow4Metabolomics.
- WP9 Hangout 2016-06-07: Call for data, prototypes and use cases. Implementation of preprocesses tools into workflows.
- WP9 Hangout 2016-08-01: Integration of tools into Galaxy and into kubernetes, discussing upcoming Deliverables, planning of attendances in upcoming workshops
- WP9 Hangout 2016-08-23:

(WP20 indicates it is joint with WP5, WP6 and WP9). We also attended two PhenoMeNal workshops: e-Infrastructures in Uppsala and W4M hackathon in Paris, and attended the PhenoMeNal meeting on Rhodes in order to arrange with the PhenoMeNal members.

Problems encountered

During our activities we encountered the following problems: The ProteoWizard VMI contains proprietary Windows software and, thus, containerising and redistribution is formally very challenging. Currently, our VMI is only able to convert raw files from certain vendors. Furthermore, we are only able to distribute the source but not the binary due to proprietary licensing of the software. During testing we found that the Galaxy framework cannot handle folders, which would make processing RAW data from some vendors simpler and would avoid creating temporary ZIP files. In an ongoing

effort, we are working closely together with the Galaxy developer community⁴⁴ to resolve this problem (pivotal in later D9.2.3).

Future plans

- Work towards development of more PhenoMeNal Virtual Machine Images (VMIs). These will cover later stages of the workflows, ultimately allowing complete metabolomics workflows for MS and NMR to be run in a PhenoMeNal cloud.
- Work is continuing on 1) Bioconductor-metabolomics, 2) Docker-batman, 3) mass IPO, 4) Metfrag, 5) Metfamily, 6) W4M-lcmsmatching, 7) W4M-xcms, 8) W4M-general, 9) NMRml-tools, 10) metabomatching and 11) Fluxomics (Iso2flux and Isodyn).
- Improving stability of containers and integration into VRE and Cloud Infrastructure as managed by WP5 and WP6.
- Writing more tutorials and set up technology demos and exemplary workflows in order to attract tool developers and users in PhenoMeNal.

2.3. Project management during this period

WP1 - Management

WP leader: EMBL-EBI

This work package is focussed on the technical, financial and administrative management and coordination of activities and PhenoMeNal consortium, to meet the main goals of the project.

The main achievements of the reporting period are:

- Annual stakeholder, scientific advisory board and consortium meeting.
- Industrial stakeholder meeting and constitution of the Industrial panel.
- Workshops, hackathons and staff-exchanges for dissemination and knowledge management.
- Documentation and publication of policies, tutorials and workflows on the PhenoMeNal wiki

⁴⁴ <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/issues/2566>

- Submission of deliverables on time
- No deviations from the project objectives.

A summary of the progress in the reporting period:

Task 1.1 Coordination at the consortium level of the ‘technical’ activities of the project.

Project Meetings

The management continued to provide project guidance via online **Monthly Status Update Meetings**. The agenda for these meetings was essentially focussed on the progress updates on individual WPs and decision making in terms of general scientific and strategic management of PhenoMeNal. Separate **WP and Cross- WP Hangouts** were used to discuss in detail the individual WPs, mitigation of risks (if any) identified, performance metrics, future plans and task distribution amongst the partners. The minutes from meetings were extensively documented in the shared Google drive for direction and future reference.

Annual Consortium meeting

The co-ordinator, EMBL-EBI organised an annual meeting of the consortium on 16th June 2016 as part of the joint 3-day event⁴⁵ in Rhodes, Greece. The meeting was attended by 27 partners with objectives to:

- Review the current status of the project
- Realign with the PhenoMeNal Objectives
- Discuss plans for PhenoMeNal sustainability and broader outreach
- Strategic future planning based on advice from autonomous advisory bodies

The meeting was divided into independent sessions to discuss in detail about the various aspects of PhenoMeNal sustainability, outreach and networking, Grid and VRC, joint research activities, privacy and ethics, and project management. For details about the agenda see **Annex 3.1**.

The meeting was kicked-off by an introduction session by the new partner CRS4⁴⁶ describing their expertise and role in contributing towards meeting the objectives of the project. Individual work package presentations were given by the WP leader/representatives on the advancements of their work package followed by an open

⁴⁵ <http://www.caramba.clinic/news/attending-phenomenal-advisory-board-meeting-rhodos/>

⁴⁶ <http://www.crs4.it>

discussion to seek counsel for current work and future directions. The consortium also considered the feedback and advice from interim review, stakeholders and SAB board while defining the future strategies and course of action for the project. A tentative plan for workshops and staff exchanges as foreseen for the 2nd year of the project was also prepared. The key action points that were concluded:

- Identification of key performance indicators for individual WPs
- Improvements of the PhenoMeNal website
- Acquiring specifications from ESFRIs, e-infrastructures, phenome centres, national infrastructures and industry on the (technical) specifications they require from PhenoMeNal and data flows they envisage. A survey was proposed to be conducted in this context.
- Need for technical documentations and guidelines in line with privacy and ethics
- Setting up a PhenoMeNal wiki page for documentations and tutorials for the consortium and user community
- Conclusions from the Data standards survey
- Defining ELSI wrappers around workflows
- Dissemination with respect to publications
- Documentation on the PhenoMeNal cloud infrastructure for the developers within the consortium

Autonomous advisory bodies meeting

The PhenoMeNal consortium aims to benefit from opinions, suggestions and feedbacks from experts and users in the scientific community, throughout the lifecycle of the project. To this end we have included autonomous advisory bodies including the SAB, user group, industrial and stakeholder panel in our management structure. As part of the WP1 objective, a stakeholder, SAB meeting and industry workshop was organised by EMBL-EBI.

Scientific Advisory Board meeting - 15th June 2016

The PhenoMeNal SAB meeting (see **Annex 3.2**) was attended by six advisors from the panel and the consortium members. PhenoMeNal sustainability and ethical constraints when handling human sensitive data were the key issues addressed before the panel for their opinions and feedback. The event was again a collaborative workspace for exchange of ideas and suggestions between the consortium and the advisory board.

The SAB provided its suggestions representing issues recognised as important by the panel. These were based on the short presentation by the partners on the individual WPs followed by discussions with the consortium.

PhenoMeNal sustainability and business models for sustainability was a major issue that was discussed extensively. The panel suggested to think bigger when it comes to sustainability and that PhenoMeNal' community could claim to be the 'one voice' expert community taking part of the metabolomics specific issues/workflows/ontologies/sops/best practices. It also suggested to make contacts networks involved in clinically certified metabolomic analysis on clinical samples in the U.S., as part of consortium's activities of interfacing with other infrastructures. Identification of key users and development of VRE based on user feedback was the key message for the PhenoMeNal VRC gateway.

Importance data standards and educating the PhenoMeNal developers early on regarding ISA and open formats was suggested with respect to the consortium's ongoing activity towards data standards and tools development.

As part of Data privacy and ethics within PhenoMeNal, it was suggested to establish contacts and align with the procedures and policies of similar projects also involved in handling sensitive data. Identification of where these guidelines are sufficient and where metabolomics implies other requirements was recommended to avoid any duplication of work.

Workshops and hackathons

- Workshop on integration of Galaxy W4M organised by CEA, March 2016
- Staff-exchange of metabolism modelling, University of Barcelona, May 2016
- UX workshop on VRE gateway, EMBL-EBI, July 2016.

Task 1.2 The overall legal, contractual, ethical, financial and administrative management of the consortium.

All the tasks related to the legal, contractual, ethical, financial and administrative management of the project are being performed as indicated in the grant agreement. Partners received on time budget transfers for hosting workshops and/or staff-exchange meetings.

Task 1.3 Coordination of knowledge management, IPS and other innovation-related activities

The project website currently hosts a Wiki page holding information regarding usage of PhenoMeNal VRE, its architecture, tutorials on deployment and continuous integration of tools, and workflows. The contents are regularly created and updated by the PhenoMeNal developer community.

Task 1.5 Maintaining communications with the commission

An interim review was organised on March 8th 2016 which was attended by representatives of all the participating organisations and the coordinator continued in making the prime link between partners and the commission regarding the schedule of the deliverables and other important communications.

PhenoMeNal Project Metrics

The project wide metrics to track the progress and impact of PhenoMeNal in the reporting period:

Work package	Performance metric	Achieved	Impact
WP3	Active participation to metabolomics-related meetings	Workshop on Computational workflow and workflow engines at Metabolomics 2016	Attended by 150 participants
WP3	Positive feedback from users at workshops	Industry Workshop, Dublin	4 members on PhenoMeNal industry panel
WP4	Working groups implemented	1	WG on metabolomics in systems biology
WP4	Number of European infrastructures/ projects represented in working groups	2 (ISBE, INSTRUCT)	Systems biology community
WP5	Number of sites	2	EMBL-EBI, UU

	supporting the project cloud		
WP5	Number of services in the project cloud	24	Successful establishment of PhenoMeNal infrastructure
WP7	Report on privacy management successfully completed and workshop outcome	ELSI workshop	Document on PhenoMeNal terms and condition (version 1.0) and D7.2
WP7	Agreed disclosure form	Work in progress for the PhenoMeNal data provider form, PhenoMeNal registration progress	Compliance to ELSI regulations
WP7	Data disclosure process and procedure established	A guidance document on handling sensitive human data was produced (D7.3)	Compliance to ELSI regulations
WP8	Data Infrastructures Survey - potential community reach	> 30400 individuals ⁴⁷	High potential reach
WP8	Data Infrastructures Survey - community engagement	132 responses	Excellent community engagement,

⁴⁷ Estimated potential reach based on sum of members of Metabolomics Society (reached via email and MetaboNews newsletter; >1500), Twitter followers of @GigaScience (5515), @ScientificData (5708) and @MetabolomicsSoc (1120), and LinkedIn groups “Metabolomics” (2120), “Clinical Metabolomics” (934), “Systems Biology” (11832), “OMICS” (1650). Figures as of 19/08/16.

			reported on in D8.1
WP8	Data Standards Collection - collation of standards, formats, specs, terminologies	40 artefacts reviewed in collection	Broad ranging review, see D8.1
WP8	Adoption and implementation by academic and commercial entities	1	National Phenome Centre/ICL to use ISA
WP9	Number of VM's available to users	>10	Successful establishment of PhenoMeNal infrastructure
WP9	Number of VM downloads	10 to 20 each ⁴⁸	The number of downloads will be logged/monitored as part of the VRE App Library and EGI AppDB integration, starting in the 2nd year of the project.

⁴⁸ During development, some of the images were pushed to <https://hub.docker.com/r/sneumann/>

3. ANNEXES

3.1. Agenda for Annual Consortium Meeting

Agenda PhenoMeNal Annual Consortium Meeting

Date: Thursday, 16th June 2016

Venue: Kamiros, Sheraton, Rhodes (Room No.-TBC)

Time: 9:00 - 16:30

Objectives:

- Review the current status of the project
- Realign with the PhenoMeNal Objectives
- Plans for PhenoMeNal sustainability and broader Outreach
- Strategic future planning based on advice from autonomous advisory bodies

9:00 - 9:15

Kick-off

Introduction of new partner - CRS4

Gianluigi Zanetti (CRS4)

9:15 - 10:00

Session 1: PhenoMeNal Sustainability

WP2 - Sustainability of PhenoMenal

Merlijn van Rijswijk (University of Leiden)

Discussions

WP2 Subtasks

10:00 - 11:00

Session 2: PhenoMeNal Outreach and Networking

WP3 - Dissemination and Outreach

Ulrich Guenther (University of Birmingham)

WP4 - Interfacing with Biomedical European Infrastructures

Antonio Rosato (CIRMMP)

Discussions

Outreach to broader community

Interfacing with other infrastructures

11:00 - 11:15

Tea/Coffee break - Kamiros Foyer

11:15 - 12:30

Session 3: PhenoMeNal GRID and VRC

WP5 - Operations and maintenance of PhenoMeNal GRID/CLOUD

Ola Spjuth (Uppsala University)

WP6 - PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway

Pablo Moreno (EMBL-EBI)

Discussions

12:30 - 13:30

Lunch - Castellania Restaurant

13:30 - 14:45

Session 4: PhenoMeNal Joint Research Activities

WP8 - Data Provenance, compliance, and integrity

David Johnson (UOXF)

WP9 - Tools, Workflows, Audit and Data Management

Steffen Neumann (IPB)

Discussions

Revisiting Workflows and use cases for PhenoMeNal

Standardization of Tools for pipelines and workflows

14:45 - 15:00

Tea/Coffee break - Kamiros Foyer

15:00 - 15:45

Session 5: Privacy and Ethics in PhenoMeNal

Robert Glen and Tim Ebbels (ICL)

Discussions

Workflows from sensitive data sets in compliance with ELSI regulations

15:45 - 16:30

Session 6: Management

WP1- Management

Namrata (EMBL-EBI)

Discussions

Planning for workshops and staff-exchanges

3.2. Agenda for SAB meeting

Agenda

PhenoMeNal Scientific Advisory Board Meeting

Date: Wednesday, 15th June 2016

Venue: Kamiros, Sheraton, Rhodes

Time: 9:00 - 12:45

Objective:

To provide independent advice and peer review on PhenoMeNal's strategy and progress, strategies for sustainability and ethical constraints

9:00 - 9:25

Introduction

Tour de table

Quick introduction by the participants

PhenoMeNal overview

Chris Steinbeck - (Coordinator PhenoMeNal, EMBL-EBI)

9:25 - 10:15

Session 1: PhenoMeNal Networking: sustainability, outreach and interfacing with other European Infrastructures

WP2 - Sustainability of PhenoMeNal

Merlijn (University of Leiden)

WP3 – Dissemination and Outreach

Ulrich (University of Birmingham) – (could not attend due to flight delay)

WP4 - Interfacing with Biomedical European Infrastructures

Antonio Rosato (CIRMMP)

10:15 - 10:45

Session 2: PhenoMeNal Services: operation and maintenance of PhenoMeNal Grid and PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community

WP5 - Operations and maintenance of PhenoMeNal GRID/CLOUD

Ola Spjuth (Uppsala University)

WP6 - PhenoMeNal Virtual Research Community Gateway

Pablo Moreno (EMBL-EBI)

10:45 - 11:00

Tea/Coffee break - Kamiros Foyer

11:00 - 11:30

Session 3: PhenoMeNal joint research activities: PhenoMeNal data standards, tools and data management

WP8 - Data Provenance, compliance, and integrity

David Johnson (UOXF)

WP9 - Tools, Workflows, Audit and Data Management

Steffen Neumann (IPB)

11:30 - 11:45

Session 4: Privacy and Ethics in PhenoMeNal

WP7- Privacy and Ethics

Robert Glen and Tim Ebbels (ICL)

11:45 - 12:45

Discussions and Feedback from SAB

Appointment of PhenoMeNal Ethics Advisor
